

Electrochemical Behaviour of *N'*-Benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-one

P. VENKATARAMANA, B. SATHYA SURYANARAYANA, L. K. RAVINDRANATH*,
V. SESHAGIRI and S. BRAHMAJI RAO

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003

Manuscript received 18 October 1989, accepted 11 May 1990

Benzeneazopyrazolin-5-ones (1-4) exhibit a well-defined reduction wave at DME and a cathodic peak at HMDE in Britton-Robinson buffers containing 40% (v/v) dimethylformamide. The products of electrolysis have been characterised and a plausible mechanism has been suggested.

THE chemistry¹ and wide range of pharmaceutical properties² of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives have been cited in literature. Keeping this in view, the electrochemical behaviour of benzeneazo-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (1-4) are studied at dropping mercury electrode (DME) and hanging mercury electrode (HMDE).

- 1; R=H, 3; R=OCH₃
2; R=CH₃, 4; R=Cl

Experimental

N'-Benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared by the reported method³. The purity of all compounds were tested by tlc and elemental analysis. Britton-Robinson buffers were prepared by adopting standard procedures.

Procedure: Dimethylformamide (A.R., H₂O; 0.02%) was purified by distilling over P₂O₅. Stock solutions (1 × 10⁻² M) of all the compounds were prepared in DMF (A.R.). Britton-Robinson buffers and various supporting electrolytes were prepared in double-distilled water. The polarograms of solution containing 1 × 10⁻² M substrate (10 ml), dimethylformamide (3.0 ml), 1.0 M supporting electrolyte (10 ml) and appropriate buffer solution (5 ml) were taken in the wider limb of the Lingane H-type cell. Purified nitrogen gas was bubbled for 10-15 min before recording the polarogram.

The number of electrons (*n*) involved in the reduction was determined by the method of Devries and Kroon⁴. The temperature coefficient was determined by Nejedly's method⁵.

The polarograms were recorded at 30 ± 0.2° on an Elico dc polarograph. pH measurement was made with an Elico digital pH meter. A saturated calomel electrode and a platinum foil were used as reference and counter electrodes respectively. The capillary characteristics were 180 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/3} at *h* = 50 cm. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded using PAR 173 potentiostat in conjunction with a RE 0074 X-Y recorder. A SMDE 303 hanging mercury drop electrode with drop area of 0.0096 cm² was used as working cathode for cyclic voltammetric experiments. A single compartment cell with silver wire as reference electrode and platinum as counter electrode was used. The half-wave potentials in polarography are not directly comparable with peak potentials with CVM as the reference electrodes in the two cases are different.

Results and Discussion

Polarography: All the compounds (1-4) gave a single four-electron reduction wave in the pH range 2.10-10.10 (Table 1). Polarograms of the compounds are shown in Fig. 1. The polarographic wave was found to be diffusion-controlled as seen from the linear plots of *i*_a vs \sqrt{h} and the low value of temperature coefficient (1.6% per degree). The wave was irreversible as shown by log plots and shift in *E*_{1/2} towards more negative potentials with increase in depolariser concentration. The pH (2.10-7.10) dependence of *E*_{1/2} indicated the participation of protons in the reduction process which suggested that the fast proton transfer precedes the main electrode process. Thus, the reduction mechanism shown in Scheme 1 may be proposed. At pH values 8.10-10.10, the *E*_{1/2} becomes independent of pH. This means that

Fig. 1. Polarograms of *N'*-benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in aqueous dimethylformamide (40%, v/v) at pH 4.10.

protons do not take part in the reduction process. The polarographic wave corresponding to the reduction of azo group seems to be not due to the simple and straight forward reduction of azo group for the following reasons. (i) The half-wave potential observed is more negative than that generally expected for the reduction of simple azo group⁶ (ii) The behaviour of the wave observed is in good agreement with the reported behaviour of compounds containing the hydrazono linkage⁷.

TABLE 1 - EFFECT OF pH ON $E_{1/2}$ AND WAVE HEIGHT

[Pyrazolin-5-ones] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium = Aqueous dimethylformamide, 40% (v/v)

pH	Half-wave potential V vs S.C.E				Wave height (μA)			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
2.10	0.59	0.62	0.65	0.56	8.0	6.2	8.0	6.8
3.10	0.65	0.69	0.74	0.62	7.5	5.9	6.0	6.1
4.10	0.76	0.82	0.85	0.72	7.8	5.8	6.2	6.2
5.10	0.85	0.92	0.94	0.82	8.0	5.8	6.5	6.3
6.10	0.98	1.02	1.05	0.95	7.3	5.6	6.5	6.5
7.10	1.00	1.04	1.09	0.98	6.8	5.3	5.9	5.7
8.10	1.04	1.08	1.13	1.02	6.5	5.1	5.2	5.2
9.10	1.04	1.08	1.13	1.02	6.5	5.1	5.2	5.2
10.10	1.04	1.08	1.13	1.02	6.5	5.1	5.2	5.2

The foregoing discussion and the position of the wave on the potential axis indicate that the wave is attributed to reduction of azo group in hydrazone form.

Cyclic voltammetry: The cyclic voltammetric data of 1-4 are presented in Table 2 and some typical cyclic voltammograms of *N'*-benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-one are shown in Fig. 2 at a sweep rate of 0.100 Vs^{-1} . All the cyclic voltammograms taken in buffered dimethylformamide-water mixtures containing 40% (v/v) dimethylformamide in the pH range studied, showed a single cathodic peak in the forward scan corresponding to the reduction. The absence of the anodic peak indicated the irreversible nature of the electrode process. This is further established by the negative shift in the peak potentials with

TABLE 2 - CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-4 AT pH VALUES 4.10 AND 8.10

[Concentration] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium = Aqueous dimethylformamide, 40% (v/v)

Compd. no.	Sweep rate Vs^{-1}	$E_{p,c}$ V	$-E_{p,c}$ inv V	$i_{p,c}$ μA	$i_{p,c}$ inv μA	pH 4.10	
1	0.020	0.82	0.75	3.2	0.30		
	0.050	0.82	0.75	3.9	0.50		
	0.100	0.84	0.78	4.5	0.80		
	0.200	0.87	0.80	5.1	1.50		
2	0.020	0.86	0.70	2.96	0.65		
	0.050	0.86	0.72	3.10	0.65		
	0.100	0.87	0.73	3.60	0.60		
	0.200	0.90	0.75	4.00	0.65		
3	0.020	0.88	0.70	2.00	0.55		
	0.050	0.88	0.70	3.50	0.60		
	0.100	0.91	0.72	4.20	0.90		
	0.200	0.94	0.74	4.90	1.10		
4	0.020	0.75	0.60	2.10	0.80		
	0.050	0.77	0.62	2.20	0.85		
	0.100	0.79	0.65	2.70	0.95		
	0.200	0.83	0.69	2.30	1.10		
						pH 8.10	
1	0.020	1.07	-	2.60	-		
	0.050	1.09	-	2.30	-		
	0.100	1.13	-	1.90	-		
	0.200	1.17	-	1.60	-		
2	0.020	1.18	-	2.80	-		
	0.050	1.18	-	2.50	-		
	0.100	1.30	-	1.90	-		
	0.200	1.34	-	1.60	-		
3	0.020	1.21	-	2.60	-		
	0.050	1.21	-	2.50	-		
	0.100	1.24	-	2.20	-		
	0.200	1.29	-	1.80	-		
4	0.020	1.05	-	2.60	-		
	0.050	1.05	-	2.50	-		
	0.100	1.07	-	2.10	-		
	0.200	1.10	-	1.80	-		

TABLE 3 - MILLICOULOMETRIC DATA ON [*N'*-BENZOYL-3-METHYL-4-(BENZENEAZO) 2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

[Depolariser] = $1.0 \text{ mol } M^{-1}$ (1.0 ml)

Current μA	t s	n -Value
pH 4.10		
7.8	0	-
6.7	7 200	3.8
6.3	10 800	4.08
pH 8.10		
6.5	0	-
5.7	7 200	3.7
5.4	10 800	3.9

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of *N'*-benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-one ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in aqueous dimethylformamide (40%, v/v) at pH values 4.10 and 8.10.

increasing sweep rate. The reduction is shown to be diffusion-controlled in the pH range 2.10–7.10 by linear plots of peak current i_p vs $\nu^{1/2}$ passing through the origin. A cathodic peak during anodic cycle was observed in pH range 2.10–6.10. These peaks are known as inverted peaks and are generally observed in organic polarography⁸⁻¹⁴. All the compounds exhibited inverted peaks under the experimental conditions. The inverted peaks are generally attributed to the (i) movement of mercury electrode surface due to uneven drop polarisation, which bears similarity to the approach and explanation of the polarographic maximum of the first kind⁹ and (ii) inhibition of electrode reaction as consequence of the coverage of the electrode by a product of the electrode reaction^{10,12,13}.

If the peak is traced to the second possibility, its intensity is expected to increase with decreasing sweep rate, since the build up of the intermediate is favoured generally by decreasing the sweep rate. The results in the present study do not conform to this. Moreover, a significant polarographic maximum is observed for these compounds under the chosen experimental conditions. It therefore seems that the inverted peak is due to the movement of the electrode surface. This is further substantiated by the fact that neither an inverted peak in the CVM nor a maximum in the polarographic reduction wave is observed in alkaline solutions.

Coulometry: Microcoulometric experiments were carried out in Britton-Robinson buffers

containing 40% (v/v) dimethylformamide. The number of electrons involved in the reduction of 1 are 3.95 ± 0.01 and 3.90 ± 0.07 at pH values 4.10 and 8.10 respectively.

Controlled potential electrolysis: The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in a Lingane H-type cell¹⁵. A large pool of mercury was used as the cathode at the bottom of the large compartment and a similar pool of mercury at the bottom of the smaller compartment served as an anode. The cathode compartment was filled with 0.01M *N'*-benzoyl-3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (20 ml) of dimethylformamide (A.R.; 20 ml) and 1.0 M KCl (20 ml) and buffer (pH 4.10; 40 ml). A potential of 0.70 V was applied and maintained by the manual control of the output from the battery. Progress of the electrolysis was followed by recording the decrease in current with time and the number of electrons per molecule was computed from $i-t$ curves following the procedure outlined by Lingane and found to be $4e^-$. After disconnecting the electrolysis cell, 1 ml of resulting solution was

Scheme 1

withdrawn and the presence of aniline in this solution was revealed by standard spot test¹⁶. The remaining reaction mixture was partially evaporated on a water-bath to half its volume, allowed to cool to room temperature and extracted with ether. The ether layer was evaporated under reduced pressure and the remaining yellow crystals were identified as *N'*-benzoyl-3-methyl-4-amino-2-pyrazoline-5-one (Found: C, 59.8; H, 4.90; N, 18.9. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2$ calcd. for: C, 60.8; H, 5.06; N, 19.3%); λ_{max} (KBr) 1595 (C=N), 1670 (C=O cyclic), 3250 (NH stretch), 3010 (C-CH₃), 1540 and 1590 cm^{-1} (aromatic character).

Mechanism: Based on the above results, a mechanism is proposed for the reduction of 1-4 (Scheme 1). The mechanisms are consistent with the earlier mechanisms suggested for the reduction of other azomethine groups¹⁷.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur, for facilities.

References

1. L. KNORR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 546.
2. A. R. SURREY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3105; P. N. BHARAGAVA and M. R. CHAURASIA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, **1**, 68, 30, 125; C. R. ENSOR and G. CHAIN, *Arch. Neurol. Psychiat.*, 1948, **62**, 857; H. D. TROUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3436; R. P. RAO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 576; M. K. ROUT and H. K. PUJARI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **13**, 1413; M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 690; S. CHANDRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1967, **40**, 2422; H. TAINYAMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **74**, 113; G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 354.
3. H. G. GRAG and C. PRAKASH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 801.
4. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2484.
5. V. NEJEDLY, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1922, **1**, 319.
6. B. NYGARD, *Arkiv. Kem.*, 1962, **20**, 163; YU. P. KITAEV and A. B. ARBUZOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Otd. Khim. Nauk.*, 1960, 1405 (*Chem. Abstr.* 1961, **55**, 440); YU. P. KITAEV and T. V. TROPOLSKAYA, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Otd. Khim. Nauk.*, 1963, **3**, 454 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968 **59**, 7347); YU. P. KITAEV, I. M. SKREBKOVA and L. I. MASLOVA, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1970, **10**, 2194 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 14233).
7. H. M. FAHMY and M. H. ELNAGDI, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 255; M. H. ELNAGDI and H. M. FAHMY, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1977, **84**, 149; M. A. MORSI, A. M. A. HELMY and H. M. FAHMY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 495.
8. D. A. TYSSEE, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1971, **30**, 14.
9. D. A. TYSSEE and M. M. BAIZER, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1971, **188**, 1420; P. TISSOT and P. MARGARETHA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 1040.
10. K. S. V. SANTHANAM and A. J. BARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2669.
11. B. FLEET and R. D. JEE, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1970, **25**, 397.
12. P. MARGARETHA and P. TISSOT, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979, **39**, 127; I. M. KOLTHOFF and S. KIHARA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 1003; D. M. LAPERRIERE, W. F. CARROLL, JR., B. C. WILLETT, E. C. TROP and D. G. PETERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 7561.
13. M. C. GIORDANO, B. A. LOPEZ and R. SERENO, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979 **101**, 39.
14. C. NANJUNDAIAH and R. NARAYAN, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979, **103**, 295.
15. J. J. LINGANE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **47**, 1916.
16. F. FEIGL, "Spot Test", 4th. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1954, Vol. 2, p 10.
17. M. A. MORSI and A. M. A. HELMY, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1983, **148**, 123; L. K. RAVINDRANATH, S. R. RAMADAS and S. B. RAO, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1983, **28**, 601; D. VASUDEVAN, S. R. RAMADAS, C. S. VENKATACHALAM and C. KALIDAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 810.